

Effects of Head Headteachers' Interpersonal Skills on Students' Academic...

Effects of Head Headteachers' Interpersonal Skills on Students' Academic Achievement at Elementary Level

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Abstract

The study's primary goal was to investigate how head teachers' interpersonal abilities affected their pupils' academic performance. The study intended to explore the impact of headteachers' interpersonal skills on students' academic accomplishment and the relationship between academic achievement and headteachers' interpersonal skills. The study's character was primarily descriptive, and data gathering involved employing a survey methodology. For this purpose, the researcher administered a self-developed questionnaire consisting of 25 items from the relevant literature, to find out the effects of head teachers' interpersonal skills on students' academic achievement. Two experts from education department of Mohi-ud-din Islamic University examined the questionnaire, and the reliability coefficient registered a value of 0.85. Data was collected through the simple random sampling technique from, 331 male students of 8th-grade public schools from Tehsil Baluch, District Sudhnooti Azad Kashmir. The data-gathering process involved the researcher making in-person visits to the selected schools. The researcher applied simple linear regression to analyze the data. After analysis of data, it was found that headteachers' interpersonal skills create positive effects on students' academic achievement.

Keywords: Interpersonal skills, students' academic achievement, Elementary Level.

Introduction

Interpersonal skills refer to the abilities and qualities that enable a headteacher to interact, communicate, and develop relationships with a variety of stakeholders in an educational setting. These skills are crucial for creating a positive and productive learning environment, nurturing collaboration, and supporting the academic and personal growth of students.

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Interpersonal skills are crucial not only for fostering relationships, but also for inducing the school's culture and, ultimately, for affecting students' academic achievement and personal growth. A headteacher with excellent interpersonal skills can foster a supportive and nurturing school environment that improves the educational experience for all students (Murphy, 2003).

The interpersonal skills of headteachers involve a range of competencies and qualities that facilitate their ability to engage in effective interaction, communication, and the establishment of constructive relationships with diverse stakeholders within an educational institution. The acquisition of these abilities is crucial in cultivating a school atmosphere that is characterized by collaboration, support, and productivity. These skills facilitate the development of constructive connections, cultivate a nurturing educational milieu, and enhance academic achievement for both students and the broader school community (Crow & Weindling, 2010).

Interpersonal skills of a headteacher at the elementary level are essential for building relationships, resolving conflicts, motivating students, and fostering a positive and inclusive school culture. These skills enhance the educational experience and significantly influence students' academic achievement (Charles, John, & Wilson, 2018).

Academic performance is a subject of extensive research due to its significant theoretical and practical consequences. It is associated with achieving notable success in education, resulting in both public recognition and tangible accomplishments, such as professional and overall performance. (Rantissi, 2015).

The relationship between a headteacher's interpersonal skills and a student's academic achievement can be significant and multi-layered. While several factors contribute to student performance, the headteacher's interpersonal skills play a vital role in creating a positive and conducive learning environment. Interpersonal abilities wield a notable impact on both the school environment and the academic performance of students, it is just one component of effective school leadership. Other factors, such as curriculum, teaching methods, resources, and community support, also play critical roles in determining student outcomes. The impact of a headteacher's interpersonal skills may vary depending on the specific context and the overall quality of the educational system (Mugizi & Kemeru, 2022).

Study Objectives

The current study encompassed the subsequent research objectives;

- i. To discover the relationship between headteachers' interpersonal skills and students' academic achievement.
- ii. To explore the effect of headteachers' interpersonal skills on students' academic achievement.

To achieve research objectives, following hypotheses were made;

- i. H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between headteachers' interpersonal skills and students' academic achievement.
- ii. H₀₂: There is no significant effect of headteachers' interpersonal skills on students' academic achievement.

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Review of Literature

Mehmood, et al. (2019), found that the connection between headteachers and learners contributes positively to students' academic achievements. They contend that the interaction between headteachers and students can influence the success of learners in educational settings (Mbogori,2012), and also found that A detrimental interpersonal relationship among headteachers, teachers, and learners, leading to conflicts, delays students' abstract success. They conceptualized conflict as the measure of adverse interactions between teachers and learners.

Cliffe (2011), The researcher examined, how the rapport between headteachers and learners impacts learning in secondary schools. The researcher asserted that the headteacher's perspective on the teacher-learner relationship can affect the teaching quality, which in turn influences students' emotional involvement in educational environments and their academic achievements.

The study of Wadsworth (2012), revealed headteachers, who maintain positive relationships with learners, tend to have students with moderate academic achievements in educational settings. Additionally, the researcher observed that a negative interpersonal relationship between headteachers and learners results in underachievement, while an inconsistent teacher-learner relationship does not consistently correlate with students' academic performance. They argued that the connection between headteachers and students enhances learner engagement, which, in turn, yields positive outcomes in terms of attention and completing educational tasks.

Several studies failed to establish a significant link between the interpersonal relationships of headteachers and learner's academic achievement. Ismail, et al. (2020) utilized intimacy, conflict, and dependency as three elements within the headteacher and student scale inventory. This research revealed a moderate yet statistically insignificant relationship between the rapport of headteachers and academic achievements of the learners.

Interpersonal Skills of Headteachers

1. **Effective Communication:** Headteachers must be adept at both verbal and non-verbal communication. Headteachers should convey information, listen actively to others, and use appropriate communication channels for different situations (Southworth, 2002). Effective communication skills are essential for a headteacher in fostering a positive and productive school environment, promoting collaboration, and supporting the overall success of students and the school community. Effective communication skills empower headteachers to lead by example, create a positive learning environment, and ensure that students, teachers, and parents are informed and engaged in the educational process (Ndinza, 2015).
2. **Active Listening:** Listening attentively to the concerns and perspectives of others, including students, teachers, and parents, is crucial. This helps headteachers better understand their needs and make informed decisions. The role of active listening skills in a headteacher's interaction with students plays a significant role in student's academic achievement and overall educational experience (Saltmarsh, 2014). Active listening skills of a headteacher are instrumental in creating a supportive and motivating learning environment that positively impacts students' academic achievement. By actively listening to students, headteachers can build stronger relationships, provide personalized support, and foster a

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culture of trust and collaboration within the school community, all of which contribute to student's success in their educational journey (Kambeya, 2008).

4. **Empathy:** Empathy is a crucial skill for a headteacher to possess as it can significantly influence students' academic achievement and overall well-being. Being able to empathize with the challenges and emotions of students, staff, and parents allows headteachers to build rapport and demonstrate genuine care and concern (Wahlstrom & Louis, 2008). Empathy is a powerful skill for a headteacher to possess, as it not only enhances students' emotional well-being but also contributes significantly to their academic achievement. An empathetic headteacher creates an environment where students feel valued, supported, and motivated to excel academically, ultimately leading to improved educational outcomes (Slater, Garcia, & Mentz, 2018).

5. **Conflict Resolution:** Conflict resolution skills are crucial for a headteacher because they play a significant role in students' academic achievement. Effective conflict resolution creates a positive and harmonious school environment that is conducive to learning and personal growth. Headteachers should possess conflict resolution skills to address disputes and disagreements within the school community fairly and constructively (Wadsworth, 2012). Conflict resolution skills of a headteacher are essential for maintaining a positive and conducive learning environment, promoting healthy teacher-student relationships, and reducing stress and distractions that can hinder academic achievement. By effectively addressing conflicts, headteachers contribute to a more harmonious school culture that supports students' academic success and overall well-being (Cotton, 2003).

6. **Cultural Sensitivity:** Cultural sensitivity skills are essential for a headteacher because they play a significant role in student's academic achievement and overall educational experience, especially in diverse and multicultural school environments. Recognising and respecting cultural diversity among students and families is important (Stoynoff, 2017). Headteachers should be sensitive to different cultural backgrounds and adapt their communication and interactions accordingly. Cultural sensitivity skills are vital for headteachers in creating an inclusive, respectful, and supportive school environment that positively impacts students' academic achievement. By recognizing and valuing the diverse cultural backgrounds of their students, headteachers contribute to a more equitable and enriching educational experience for all (Southworth, 2002).

7. **Approachability:** Creating an open-door policy and fostering an environment where individuals feel comfortable approaching the headteacher with questions, concerns, or ideas is essential (Wahlstrom & Louis, 2008). The approachability skill of a headteacher plays a crucial role in students' academic achievement and overall educational experience. When a headteacher is approachable, it creates a positive and open school environment that can lead to several benefits for students (Witziers, Bosker & Krüger, 2003). The approachability skill of a headteacher is essential for creating a welcoming and supportive school environment that enhances students' academic achievement. It encourages open communication, fosters trust, and empowers students to seek help and engage actively in their education, ultimately contributing to their success in school (Kasa, 2020).

8. **Collaboration:** Collaboration skills enable headteachers to work effectively with teachers, other school administrators, and external stakeholders to implement educational initiatives and support students' needs. The collaboration skills of a headteacher are

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instrumental in creating a collaborative school culture that fosters academic achievement. When headteachers work closely with teachers, staff, parents, and the community, they can develop a holistic approach to education that addresses the diverse needs of students, ultimately contributing to their academic success and overall well-being (James, David, & Thinguri, 2014).

9. **Problem-Solving:** Identifying challenges and finding practical solutions is vital for addressing issues related to student achievement, school policies, and administrative matters. Problem-solving skills are essential for a headteacher because they have a significant impact on student's academic achievement and overall educational experience. problem-solving skills of a headteacher are instrumental in creating an environment where academic challenges are identified, addressed, and resolved effectively (Wadsworth, 2012). When headteachers apply problem-solving skills to support teachers and students, it can lead to improved academic achievement and contribute to a positive and successful educational experience for all students (Witziers, Bosker & Krüger, 2003).

10. **Motivation and Leadership:** Motivation and leadership abilities exert a substantial influence on students' academic performance and their overall educational journey. Inspiring and motivating students and staff is a central aspect of effective leadership. Headteachers should lead by example and encourage a positive learning environment. The motivation and leadership skills of a headteacher are instrumental in creating a school environment where students are inspired, supported, and empowered to achieve their academic goals. These skills can positively influence student engagement, performance, and overall academic success, contributing to a thriving educational community (West, Jackson, & Hopkins, 2013).

11. **Relationship-building:** Relationship-building skills of a headteacher refer to their ability to establish and maintain positive, effective, and productive relationships with various stakeholders within the school community. These skills are crucial for fostering a supportive and inclusive school environment, promoting collaboration, and enhancing the overall educational experience for student Relationship building skills are not only essential for improving the overall school culture but also for creating an environment where students and staff feel valued, heard, and supported (Lingard, & Christie, 2003).

These skills enable headteachers to collaborate effectively with all stakeholders to enhance the educational experience and contribute to student's academic success and personal development. The interpersonal skills of a headteacher contribute, a critical role in shaping the elementary school environment and influencing students' academic success. By fostering trusting relationships, promoting effective communication, and creating a supportive atmosphere, headteachers with strong interpersonal skills can inspire motivation, resolve conflicts constructively, and provide individualized support to students. Additionally, their ability to engage with parents, collaborate with teachers, and promote inclusivity contributes to a positive school culture that enhances the overall learning experience and facilitates academic achievement for elementary students (Saltmarsh, 2014).

Students Academic Achievement

Student academic achievement refers to a student's level of success and performance in educational endeavours, typically measured through various assessment methods such as grades, standardized tests, and academic awards. It encompasses a wide range of academic

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outcomes Academic achievement is often used to evaluate a student's overall output and potential for future success in their educational journey and beyond, including their readiness for higher education or entry into the workforce. It can vary from one educational level to another, from primary and secondary education to higher education and beyond, depending on the specific goals and expectations of the educational institution or program (Singh, 2011). Academic achievement represents the advancement toward the objective of acquiring educational skills, materials, and knowledge, typically across various subject areas. It pertains to success in educational contexts, distinct from the broad acquisition of knowledge in non-academic settings (Hakimi, Hejazi & Lavasani, 2011).

Stoyhoff (2017), asserted that students' academic encompasses a wide range of outcomes and measures, including grades, standardized test scores, course completion rates, and other indicators of a student's educational progress. Academic achievement is an assessment of the extent to which a student or institution has attained their educational objectives, whether they are short-term or long-term in nature. For individual students, achievement can be gauged by factors such as their grade point average, while institutions may assess achievement by looking at metrics like graduation rates.

This review explored the influence of positive behaviours displayed by headteachers, including the cultivation of favourable interpersonal connections with students, on their academic accomplishments. The study revealed that when headteachers establish positive relationships with students and promote their active involvement in educational environments, learners generally experience increased satisfaction and motivation to learn.

Research Methodology

Methodology describes the research design, sources of data, the data collection method, the sampling procedure and data analysis techniques to be employed.

Research Design

The present study was descriptive and quantitative. The academic achievement of students was operated as the dependent variable, whereas the interpersonal skills of headteachers were considered as the independent variable.

Population of the Study

The study's population consisted of all 2,375 8th-grade students attending Government Boys Schools in District Sudhnuti, AJ&K, Pakistan. Elementary education in this context covers classes ranging from one to eight.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The research employed a simple random sampling method to choose its samples. Utilizing this technique, 33, 8th -grade male students were randomly chosen as the research sample. The sample size was determined following the guidelines outlined by Krejcie and Morgan in 1970, page 608, using a table for calculating the sample size for a known population. As indicated by Easton and McColl in 2015, simple random sampling techniques are recommended for studying a diverse or heterogeneous population.

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Instrumentation

The researcher utilized a self-constructed questionnaire that employed a five-point Likert scale to collect data. This questionnaire was developed after a comprehensive examination and analysis of the pertinent literature. It comprised 25 items designed in alignment with the objectives of the current study.

Validity and Consistency of the tools

The researcher sought validation of the research tools from experts in the field of education. Additionally, to assess the internal reliability of the items, Cronbach's Alpha was applied in this study. The obtained Cronbach's Alpha value was 0.85, surpassing the threshold of 0.7, which is considered very good.

Data Collection

Data collection was conducted by the researcher through personal visits to the sample institutions. The member completes the questionnaire after the researcher has provided instructions to the group on, how to conduct the survey.

Data Analysis and Explanation

For purpose of data analysis, the researcher used the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS-23). The researcher applied Simple Linear Regression for the analysis of data.

Results

Analysis of Sub-scales of Headteachers Interpersonal Skills with Students Academic Achievement Indicators.

Table 1

Analysis of Effect of Headteachers Communication Skills with Students' Grades.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson	F-Statistic
1	.073	.005	.003	.10874	2.357	2.403

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients B	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t-value	Sig.
(Constant)	2.013		30.754	.000
1 Effect of HT Communication skill on Students' grades	.053	.073	1.429	.154

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- a. Predictor Variable: Effect of HT Communication Skills
- b. Dependent Variable: Students Grades

Table 1 presents the results of the regression analysis, which examined the impact of headteachers' communication skills on students' grades. The communication skills of headteachers were regarded as the independent variable in this analysis, while student grades served as the dependent variable. There is a significant correlation between the communication skills of headteachers and students' grades, according to the findings. Based on the Durbin-Watson value of 2.357, it can be concluded that the data does not exhibit any autocorrelation. The regression analysis generated a reasonable fit, as indicated by the F value of 2.043. Furthermore, the p-value provides further evidence that the communication skills of headteachers have a significant impact on students' grades. The p-value is .154, which, at a 95% confidence interval, is less than .05. R is equal to 0.073, while R² equals 0.005. The R² value signifies that the variance in students' grades is described for by 0.005% of the variance in the independent variable (the impact of headteachers' communication skills). Given that the p-value is below 0.05, it is possible to deduce that the communication skills of headteachers have a statistically significant impact on the grades of their students.

Table 2

Analysis of Effect of Headteachers Communication Skills with Students' Participation in Class Discussion.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson	F-Statistic
1	.072	.004	.002	.10775	2.256	2.102

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients B	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t-value	Sig.
1	(Constant)	2.012	.062		30.732	.000
	Effect of HT communication skills on students' participation in class discussion	.051	.036	.072	1.424	.151

- a. Predictor Variable: Impact of HT Communication Skills
- b. Dependent Variable: Students participation in class discussion

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Table 2 shows result of regression analysis, effect of headteachers' communication skills on students' participation in class discussion. Communication skill of headteachers was treated as independent variable and students' participation in class discussion was taken as dependent variable. There is a positive connection between the communication abilities of headteachers and the level of student participation in class discussions. The Durbin-Watson statistic, with a value of 2.256, indicates the absence of autocorrelation in the dataset. The F value of 2.102 suggests that the regression analysis model exhibits a favourable level of fitness. The p-value serves as an indicator of the statistical significance of the relationship between the communication skills of headteachers and the level of student participation in class discussions. The p-value obtained from the statistical analysis is 0.151, which is lower than the commonly used significance level of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at a 95% confidence range. The coefficient of correlation (R) is found to be 0.072, indicating a weak positive linear relationship between the variables. Additionally, the coefficient of determination (R^2) is calculated to be 0.004, suggesting that only 0.4% of the variation in the dependent variable can be explained by the independent variable. The coefficient of determination, R^2 , suggests that the independent variable, namely the headteachers' communication skill, accounts for a mere 0.004% of the variability observed in the dependent variable, which pertains to students' engagement in class discussion. Based on the obtained p-value of less than .05, it may be inferred that there exists a statistically significant relationship between the headteacher's communication skills and students' engagement in class discussions.

Table 3

Analysis of Effect of Headteacher,s Empathy with Students' Grades.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson	F-Statistic
1	.039	.001	-.001	.14664	1.723	.572

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients B	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t-value	Sig.
	(Constant)	2.033	.088		23.029	.000
1	Effect of HT Empathy on Students' Grades	-.038	.050	-.039	-.756	.450

a. Predictor Variable: Impact of HT Empathy

b. Dependent Variable: Students Grades

Table 3 shows result of, effect of headteachers' empathy with student's grades. Empathy of

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elementary school heads was treated as independent variable and student's grades were taken as dependent variable. The table presenting the model summary indicates that the R value is 0.039 and the R² value is 0.001. This finding suggests that the independent variable, namely the level of empathy exhibited by headteachers, accounts for a minimal proportion of the variance observed in the dependent variable, which pertains to pupils' academic performance, namely their grades. The Durbin-Watson statistic has a value of 1.723. The value of 1.5 indicates the absence of autocorrelation in the dataset. The F value of .572 indicates a satisfactory level of model fitness. The obtained p-value of .450 indicates statistical significance at the 95% confidence level, as it is less than the predetermined alpha level of .05. The regression analysis results indicate a substantial relationship between headteachers' empathy and teachers' communication skills. On the basis of findings, it can be concluded that there is a positive correlation between the level of empathy demonstrated by headteachers and the academic performance of students.

Table 4

Analysis of Effect of Headteachers Empathy with Students Participation in Class Discussion.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson	F-Statistic
1	.025	.016	.009	.19675	1.720	7.278

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t-value	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	1.725	.118		14.567	.000
	Effect of HT Empath on students' participation in class discussion	.035	.067	.027	.526	.232

a. Predictor Variable: Impact of HT Empathy

b. Dependent Variable: Students participation in class discussion

Table 4 shows result of regression analysis, effect of headteachers' empathy with students' participation in class discussion. The independent variable in this study was the level of empathy exhibited by headteachers, while the dependent variable was the extent of students' participation in class discussions. There is a significant relationship between the empathy

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abilities possessed by headteachers and the level of student participation observed during class discussions. The Durbin-Watson statistic has a value of 1.720, indicating the absence of autocorrelation in the dataset. The F value of 7.278 suggests that the regression analysis model exhibits a satisfactory level of fitness. The p-value serves as an indicator of the statistical significance of the relationship between the empathy skill levels of headteachers and the extent of students' participation in class discussions. The p-value obtained from the statistical analysis is 0.232, which is lower than the predetermined significance level of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at a 95% confidence range. The R value is 0.025 and the R^2 value is 0.004. The R^2 value suggests that the independent variable, namely the headteachers' communication skills, accounts for 0.016% of the variance seen in students' participation in class discussions, which is dependent variable. Based on the obtained p-value being less than .05, it is suggested that there is significant relationship between the headteacher's empathy skill and the level of student participation in class discussions.

Table 5

Analysis of Effect of Headteachers Active Listening Skill with Students' Grades.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson	F-Statistic
1	.043	.002	.000	.10891	2.357	.523

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients B	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t-value	Sig.
1	(Constant)	1.853	.074		25.022	.000
	Effect of HT ALS skill on Students' grades	.038	.042	.046	.908	.351

- a. Predictor Variable: Impact of HTs ALS
- b. Dependent Variable: Student's Grades

Table 5 shows result of, effect of headteachers' active listening skills on student's grades. The independent variable in this study was the active listening skills of elementary school heads, whereas the dependent variable was the children's grades. The table presenting the model summary indicates that the R value is 0.043 and the R^2 value is 0.002. This implies that the independent variable, which pertains to the active listening skill of headteachers, accounts for a mere 0.002% of the variance observed in the dependent variable, namely pupils' grades. The Durbin-Watson statistic has a value of 2.537. The data demonstrates the absence of autocorrelation. The obtained F value of .523 indicates a satisfactory level of model fitness.

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The obtained p-value of .351 indicates statistical significance at the 95% confidence level, as it is greater than the conventional threshold of .05. The regression analysis results indicate a statistically significant relationship between headteachers' active listening skills and pupils' grades. So, there is a significant impact of headteachers' proficiency in active listening on the academic performance of students.

Table 6

Analysis of Effect of Headteachers Active Listening Skill with Students Participation in Class Discussion.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson	F-Statistic
1	.027	.002	.000	.21335	2.1220	.636

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t-value	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	2.148	.145		14.809	.000
	Effect of HT, ASL with students' participation in class discussion	-.075	.082	-.047	-.914	.355

a. Predictor Variable: Effect of HT ALS

b. Dependent Variable: Students participation in class discussion

Table 6 shows result of regression analysis, effect of headteachers' active listening skills on students' participation in class discussion. The independent variable in this study was the active listening abilities of headteachers, while the dependent variable was the students' participation in class discussions. On the basis of results, there is a significant relationship between the academic leadership skills (ALS) of headteachers and students' engagement in classroom discussions. The Durbin-Watson statistic has a value of 2.122, indicating the absence of autocorrelation in the dataset. The obtained F value of .636 suggests that the regression analysis model exhibits a satisfactory level of fitness. The p-value provides evidence of a statistically significant relationship between the leadership style of headteachers and pupils' engagement in classroom discussions. The calculated p-value of .355 falls below the predetermined significance level of .05 ($p < .05$) within a 95% confidence range. The R-value is 0.027, indicating a weak positive correlation, while the R^2 value is 0.002, suggesting that only a small proportion of the variance in the data can be explained by the

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independent variable. The coefficient of determination (R^2) suggests that the independent variable, namely the impact of headteachers' AL talent, accounts for a mere 0.002% of the variability observed in the dependent variable, which pertains to students' engagement in class discussion. Based on the obtained p-value being less than .05, so, there is a significant relationship between the headteacher's active listening competence and the level of student participation in class discussions.

Table 7

Analysis of Effect of Headteachers Problem Solving Skill with Students' Grades.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson	F-Statistic
1	.033	.002	.001	.14666	1.708	.455

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients B	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t-value	Sig.
	(Constant)	2.034	.100		20.402	.000
1	Effect of HT PS skill with students' grades	-.038	.056	.014	-.684	.421

a. Predictor Variable: Impact of HT Problem Solving Skill

b. Dependent Variable: Students' grades

Table 7 shows result of, effect of the headteacher's problem-solving skills on students' grades. The independent variable in this study was the problem-solving skills of elementary school heads, whereas the dependent variable was the students' grades. The table presenting the model summary indicates that the R value is 0.033 and the R^2 value is 0.002. This implies that the independent variable, namely the problem-solving skill of headteachers, accounts for a mere 0.002% of the variance observed in the dependent variable, which pertains to students' grades. The Durbin-Watson statistic has a value of 1.708. The data exhibits no evidence of autocorrelation. The F value of .455 indicates a satisfactory level of model fitness. The obtained p-value of .421 indicates statistical significance at the 95% confidence level, as it is greater than the conventional alpha level of .05. The results of the regression analysis show that there is a significant relationship between the problem-solving skills of headteachers and the academic performance of students. So according to results, there exists a notable impact of headteachers' problem-solving abilities on the academic performance of students.

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Table 8

Analysis of Effect of Headteachers Problem-Solving Skill with Students Participation in Class Discussion.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson	F-Statistic
1	.032	.002	.001	.19666	1.654	.643

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients B	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t-value	Sig.
(Constant)	1.681		11.577	.000
1 Effect of HT Problem-Solving Skills with Students' participation in class discussion	.060	.041	.695	.487

- a. Predictor Variable: Impact of HT Problem-solving skill
- b. Dependent Variable: students' participation in class discussion

Table 8 shows result of regression analysis and, effect of headteachers' PSS on students' participation in class discussion. The independent variable in this study was the problem-solving ability of headteachers, while the dependent variable was students' participation in class discussions. The relationship between the problem-solving skills of headteachers and student participation in class discussions is found to be statistically significant. A model adequacy of 0.643 is indicated by the F value of regression analysis. The P value indicates that the problem-solving skills of headteachers have a significant impact on student participation in class discussions. The obtained P value of 0.487 is below the significance level of 0.05 ($p < .05$) at the 95% confidence interval. The R value is .032, while the R^2 value is .002. The value of R^2 indicates that 0.002% of the variance in the dependent variable (students' participation in class discussion) was reported for by the independent variable (the impact of headteachers' problem-solving skills competence). Given that the p-value is below 0.05, it can be inferred that the problem-solving ability of headteachers had a statistically significant impact on students' engagement in classroom discussions.

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Table 9

Analysis of Effect of Headteachers Relationship Building Skill with Students' Grades.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson	F-Statistic
1	.026	.002	.000	.15815	1.435	.711

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients B	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t-value	Sig.
(Constant)	1.950	.108		18.141	.000
1 Effect of HT Relationship building skills on Students' Grades	-.055	.061	-.046	-.903	.361

- a. Predictor Variable: Effect of HT relationship building skills
- b. Dependent Variable: Students Grades

Table 9 presents the results of an analysis that assesses the impact of elementary school headteachers' relationship-building skills on students' grades. In this analysis, the relationship-building skills of headteachers are considered the independent variable, while students' grades are the dependent variable. The model summary table indicates that the R-squared value is 002 and the R-value is 026. This finding suggests that the independent variable, which pertains to the relationship-building skills exhibited by headteachers, simply accounts for 0.002% of the variability observed in the dependent variable, which is students' grades. Despite its relatively modest size, this percentage remains statistically significant. The regression model demonstrates a decent fit, as evidenced by the F value of 0.711. This suggests that the model adequately explains the association between the independent and dependent variables. The obtained p-value of 0.361 is statistically significant at the 95% confidence interval ($p < .05$). The findings of the regression analysis indicate that the relationship-building skills of headteachers have a positive relationship with the grades of their students.

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Table 10

Analysis of Effect of Headteachers Relationship Building Skill with Students Participation in Class Discussion.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson	F-Statistic
1	.065	.002	.005	.10864	2.432	2.732

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	t-value	Sig.
	B	Beta		
(Constant)	1.806		26.270	.000
1 Impact of HT relationship building skills with students' participation in class discussion	.061	.084	1.655	.234

- a. Predictor Variable: Impact of HT relationship building skills
- b. Dependent Variable: Students participation in class discussion

Table 10 presents the results of a regression analysis, examining the impact of headteachers' relationship-building skills on students' participation in class discussions. In this analysis, headteachers' relationship-building skills were considered the independent variable, while students' participation in class discussions served as the dependent variable. The results indicate a statistically significant effect between headteachers' relationship-building skills and students' participation in class discussions. Positively, the Durbin-Watson score of 2.432 indicates that autocorrelation is not a problem in the data. The F value is 2.732, which indicates that the regression model is a good fit, suggesting that the model effectively explains the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. With a 95% confidence interval and a p-value of 0.234, which is less than 0.05 ($p < .05$), it can be concluded that there is a statistically significant relationship between the relationship-building abilities of headteachers and students' engagement in classroom discussions. The R-value is .065, and the R-squared (R^2) value is .002. The R^2 value indicates that the independent variable (the effect of headteachers' relationship-building skills) explains only 0.002% of the variance in the dependent variable (students' participation in class discussions). Although this is a small percentage, the statistically significant p-value still suggests that there is a significant effect of headteachers' relationship-building skills on students' participation in class discussions.

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In summary, based on the p-value which is less than .05, there is a significant impact of headteachers' relationship-building skills on students' participation in class discussions.

Discussion and Conclusion

The main objective of the research was to evaluate the influence of interpersonal abilities of headteachers on student's academic achievement. The primary aim of the research was to ascertain whether there was a correlation between the interpersonal abilities of headteachers and the academic performance of their students. The study's findings indicated a noteworthy influence of headteachers' interpersonal skills on students' academic success. In other words, it was observed that headteachers' interpersonal skills have a positive impact on students' academic achievements. The results were composed by Kasa (2020) and Rantissi (2015), who found that headteachers' interpersonal skills create positive effects on students' academic achievement.

The second aim of the research was to examine the influence of the interpersonal abilities of headteachers on the scholastic achievement of students. The findings similarly revealed a significant influence of headteachers' interpersonal skills on students' academic achievement. These findings were also consistent with the findings of Singh (2011), who also found that headteachers' interpersonal skills create positive effects on students' academic achievement. Hence, the researchers concluded that there was substantial evidence indicating a robust connection between headteachers' interpersonal skills and students' academic achievement.

References

1. Abdi, A. (2014). The effect of inquiry-based learning method on students' academic achievement in a science course. *Universal journal of educational Research*, 2(1), 37-41.
2. Bezzina, C. G. (2001). The professional development of headteachers in Malta: trends and developments. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 15(3), 138-144.
3. Charles Dickens, S., John, S., & Wilson, M. M. (2018). The effect of management development on the performance of public primary school headteachers in Nakasongola District-Uganda.
4. Cliffe, J. (2011). Emotional intelligence: A study of female secondary school headteachers. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 39(2), 205-218.
5. Cotton, K. (2003). Principals and student achievement: What the research says.
6. Crow, G. M., & Weindling, D. (2010). Learning to be political: New English headteachers' roles. *Educational Policy*, 24(1), 137-158.
7. Hakimi, S., Hejazi, E., & Lavasani, M. G. (2011). The relationships between personality traits and students' academic achievement. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 29, 836-845.
8. Ismail, K., Sutarman, T., Yudhakusuma, D., & Mayasari, L. I. (2020). Social communication competence as a soft skill of the school leadership in the Archipelago region. *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 24(08), 2020.
9. James, N., David, M., & Thinguri, R. (2014). Evaluating the Impact of Primary School Headteachers' Supervisory Practices on Academic Performance in Githunguri SubCounty, Kenya. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 5(21), 47-58.
10. Kambeya, N. V. (2008). Georgia teachers' perceptions of principals' interpersonal communication skills as they relate to teacher performance.
11. Kasa, M. D. (2020). The morale of supervision: The impact of technical supervision skills of teaching and learning on teachers' self-efficacy. *International Journal of Criminology and*

Effects of Head Headteachers' Interpersonal Skills on Students' Academic...

- Sociology*, 9(1), 335-349.
12. Lingard, B. & Christie, P. (2003). *EBOOK: Leading Learning: Making Hope Practical in Schools*. McGraw-Hill Education (UK).
 13. Mbogori, J. M. (2012). Influence of headteachers' leadership styles on student discipline in public secondary schools in Nairobi province, Kenya (Doctoral dissertation, University of Nairobi, Kenya).
 14. Mehmood, T., Hassan, D. H. C., & Taresh, S. (2019). The Role of the Interpersonal Skills of the School Principals in Optimizing Positive School Climate: A Concept Paper. *International Journal of Emerging Issues in Social Science, Arts and Humanities (IJEISSAH)*, 1(2), 38-54.
 15. Mugizi, W. & Kemer, J. (2022). Headteachers' Leadership Practices and Students' Discipline in Government Aided Secondary Schools in Bushenyi-Ishaka Municipality, Uganda. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Education Research*, 4, 44-59.
 16. Murphy, D. (2003). Assessing effective interpersonal skills in prospective school leaders. *Journal of In-service Education*, 29(2), 221-236.
 17. Ndinza, K. L. (2015). *Influence of headteachers' management practices on students' academic performance in public secondary schools within Kitui Central District, Kitui County, Kenya* (Doctoral dissertation).
 18. Rantissi, G. (2015). Analyzing Teachers' Expectations of the Headteacher's Roles at an Arab-Bedouin Elementary School in South of Israel.
 19. Saltmarsh, S. (2014). "It all comes down to the leadership" and the role of the school principal in fostering parent-school engagement. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 42(4), 491-505.
 20. Singh, K. (2011). Study of achievement motivation about academic achievement of students. *International Journal of Educational Planning & Administration*, 1(2), 161-171.
 21. Slater, C. L., Garcia Garduno, J. M., & Mentz, K. (2018). Frameworks for principal preparation and leadership development: Contributions of the International Study of Principal Preparation (ISPP). *Management in Education*, 32(3), 126-134.
 22. Southworth, G. (2002). Instructional leadership in schools: Reflections and empirical evidence. *School leadership & management*, 22(1), 73-91.
 23. Stoyhoff, S. (2017). Factors associated with international students' academic achievement. *Journal of instructional psychology*, 24(1), 56.
 24. Wadsworth, T. (2012). A school leaders' professional development project The first year: Progress in researching the professional development needs of secondary school headteachers. *School Organization*, 8(3), 315-330.
 25. Wahlstrom, K. L., & Louis, K. S. (2008). How teachers experience principal leadership: The roles of professional community, trust, efficacy, and shared responsibility. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 44(4), 458-495.
 26. West, M., Jackson, D., & Hopkins, D. (2013). Learning through leadership, leadership through learning: Leadership for sustained school improvement. In *Leadership for change and school reform* (pp. 30-49). Routledge.
 27. Witziers, B., Bosker, R. J., & Krüger, M. L. (2003). Educational leadership and student achievement: The elusive search for an association. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 39(3), 398-425.
 28. Yin, H. (2019). Professional learning communities count: Examining the relationship between faculty trust and teacher professional learning in Hong Kong kindergartens. *Teaching and teacher education*, 82, 153-163.